

Montesquieu's Thought on Rule of Law-Set Issues for Political Practice in Vietnam

Phan Thi Hien ✉

Ho Chi Minh City University of Industry and Trade, Vietnam

Dinh Ngoc Thach ✉

*University of Social Sciences and Humanities, Vietnam National University,
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam*

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Abstract:

Building the State with the objective: *prosperous people, strong nation, democracy, justice and civilization* has set an indispensable requirement of the comprehensive renovation of the apparatus of Vietnam in the direction of a modern state, which is the actual reason why we choose the political thought of Montesquieu as a theoretical basis for this article.

The purpose of the article is to assess the historical significance, epochal value, positive contributions of the doctrine to theory and practice of mankind through a generalization of Montesquieu's political thought, thereby we draw lessons and the necessity of creatively applying the doctrine to the construction of the rule-of-law state in Vietnam.

To achieve this purpose, we structure the content of the article into two sections: In the first section, the article briefly outlines basic contents of the thought that is directly related to our recommendation; In the second section, from the theoretical and practical values of the doctrine, we recommend directional solutions that we believe that they will bring practical effects to the renewal of the political system in Vietnam.

With the above content, in the article, we use methods such as: qualitative analysis method, generalization and systemization method, historical - logical method, data synthesis method.

Keywords: *Thought, rule of law, Montesquieu, Vietnam.*

Introduction

Montesquieu's thought on rule of law has had a great influence on Western political thought and practice from the late eighteenth century to the present day and shaped a global politics of the future. The viewpoints on natural rights, on democracy, on state power, on political ethics, etc., especially decentralization thought become the principles of the modern rule-of-law state: combat against the autocracy, misfeasance,

corruption, dictatorship and arbitrary in the organization and exercise of state power.

Studies on Montesquieu's rule of law and creative application to the practice of building a rule-of-law state have been mentioned a lot in the world, but in Vietnam, this is a very sensitive political issue that is seldom mentioned, if any, the issue is still seen in extreme ideology.

In the world, since its appearance, Montesquieu's rule of law has been paid special attention by many researchers, politicians and

scholars who made convincing judgments and assessments, such as:

In Montesquieu's Philosophy of Liberalism, Thomas L. Pangle (1944) considers the issues on liberalism, on "multiparty democracy", "electoral politics" in Montesquieu's theory as norms of the modern political life;

Titled *Les grandes oeuvres politiques*, J.J. Chevallier (1900 - 1983) focused on presenting fundamental and core issues in Montesquieu political philosophy such as law, polity and decentralization; gave facts about the relationship, inevitable impact of politics on all other aspects and even human innate nature; at the same time explained the causes of the revolutions leading to Western democracy today and the formation of dictatorship in the modern world.

On the issue of Freedom and the Normative Force of the Law in Montesquieu's *The Spirit of the Laws*, Cory Wimberly called Montesquieu a liberal philosopher and a major influencer on the history of liberal thought. The thoughts on natural laws and natural rights have been referred by the author as the basis for proposing a pluralistic politics and principles of freedom assurance of human, etc.

These works are valuable data sources as a theoretical basis for our analysis and convincing arguments of building a realistic rule-of-law state in Vietnam. In the article: *Montesquieu's thought on rule of law – set issues for political practice in Vietnam*, we continue to selectively inherit the data sources of the above authors to research and recommend highly feasible directional solutions for the construction of a rule-of-law state in the specific conditions of Vietnam.

New points that we draw and are also conclusion in this article are as follows:

- Firstly, combine decentralization with highly appreciation of social criticism system;
- Secondly, democratize the society for overcoming the current formalistic democracy;
- Thirdly, innovate the method of controlling power.

Results and Discussion

An Overview of Montesquieu's Thought on Rule of Law

Montesquieu's political thought in general, including the thought on rule of law arose and developed in the specific historical conditions of French society in the pre-revolutionary period, the strong influence of democratic and humanistic culture in Europe; especially the severe social contradictions that were irreconcilable in French society at "night before" the revolution. The French Enlightenment movement initiated by Montesquieu expressed the extreme hatred and liberation aspiration of the French people to escape from the harsh domination of the 18th century French autocracy, in which the king held absolute power, exercised arbitrary rule by personal will, human rights, legitimate rights and interests of citizens were brutally deprived.

In that social and historical context, Montesquieu built a theory of the rule of law based on the belief that: human rights were innate natural rights, established by natural law, and not given by anyone and also could not be appropriated. Natural law preceded and was the basis for human law. He asserted: "Human is born to live in society, but can forget their fellow human beings, so legislators must remind them of their obligations by political and civil laws. Before such laws existed, there were laws of nature that created our existence" (Montesquieu, p.23). The recognition of obvious, inherent, undeprivable and indestructible equal and freedom rights of any force, thing belonging to human nature has a great historical significance that is the stimulation of the human spirit to fight for a good social space, affirming the value of freedom and sacred natural rights. During the bourgeois revolution that followed, the bourgeoisie, while raising the flag of human rights against the ruling feudal landlord class, inherited the progressive thoughts on natural rights of the Enlighteners, in particular Montesquieu's thoughts on natural rights and decentralization aimed at giving demands on freedom stemming from its economic and political position: that is, individual freedom ,

especially freedom of speech, freedom of belief, freedom of the press, freedom of assembly, association, demonstration, voting and self-nomination right. We can see this very clearly in the United States Declaration of Independence and Declaration of the Rights of the Man and of the Citizen of 1791.

Upon referring to the importance of the principle of decentralization, Montesquieu argued that, in the natural environment, people lived in a collective, harmony, love, cooperation with each other, "and peace is the first law of nature" (Montesquieu, p.23), but when participating in social life, people were always influenced by emotions and desires, constantly violated the laws of nature leading to despotism, violence and prejudice. Therefore, in order to protect the inherent sacred natural rights of human beings, Montesquieu founded the theory of decentralization with the intention that: when total power of an agency was exercised by the same holder of total power of another agency, the principle of a liberal constitution collapsed. From that, he argued that the organization of state power under the method of dividing state power was to fight autocracy, eliminate misfeasance and ensure human freedom (see Montesquieu, p. 114 – 116).

In the theory of decentralization, Montesquieu not only purely mentioned the division of power but also focused on the way of coordination among powerful bodies that used power to control power. Accordingly, each powerful bodies (legislative, executive, and judicial) was both an independent unit, and coordinated, complemented, supported, bound and controlled each other to limit power expansion. Such a principle of decentralization, in our opinion, is an expression of Montesquieu's own revolutionary and innovative spirit. Beyond other thoughts in the same period, Hobbes advocated that power was indivisible but must be given to a supreme ruler (king) to protect the freedom of the people. The power of the state, of the king was absolute, indivisible and the civilians had no power over the state. Hobbes's conception in the historical context of the seventeenth century both expressed a pessimistic view of human nature and reflected

fear at the prospect that England would be divided by the struggle for power among factions and parties. But Hobbes was wrong when Locke judged: giving absolute power to the king to secure the freedom of the people was tantamount to entrusting the peace to the clutches of lions (Locke, 2007, p. 372). In fact, Hobbes' ideal state was a typical example of an absolute monarchy in which the king's power was unlimited. However, when affirming decentralization as a principle, Locke also inevitably compromised (wanting to protect the interests of the bourgeoisie but failing to go through the shadow of autocracy); he advocated giving the ruler too much power, merging both executive power and judicial power into the king's hands. So it was easy to understand the reason why, in the theory of decentralization, Locke only divided power into two basic parts: legislative power and executive power.

Not accepting centralization of power, Montesquieu advocated the division of state power into three parts, legislative, executive and judicial. There was no concept of ultimate political power. These three rights must be divided and independent, that is, separate and independent of each other. Such three rights were assigned to different bodies that were independent of each other. Corresponding to these three powers are three bodies: legislative body was the parliament, the executive body was the government and the judicial body is the court. For this division, we thought that it was an inevitable reflection of the rule-based movement and development trend of political life.

As a proponent of the rule of law democracy, Montesquieu believed that the law was an effective tool in maintaining social order and constraining state power. According to him, the corruption of an institution stemmed from the corruption of the ruler and its crucial point was that whether or not the law was used and how it was used. He attached special importance to the law, considered the law as a prerequisite to prevent from dictatorship and avoid the destruction of society. He believed that a limited democracy established in the spirit of the rule of law was the best way to resolve social conflicts

and disagreements; harmonize interest relationships; bring equality and freedom to everyone. The democracy referred to by Montesquieu was the one that "everyone is equal as a citizen" [Montesquieu, p.88], it was the result of a covenant between the state and individuals on natural rights and freedom that were institutionalized and legalized. The set issue, according to Montesquieu, was how a democratic institution could both meet the requirements of reality and prevent democracy from being pushed too far into chaos? As shown in practical experience, not only the lack of the spirit of equality would bring about the autocracy of one ruler that event the thought on extreme equality and abuse of democracy was very dangerous (Montesquieu, p.87-88). His optimal solution was to build a democracy in combination with elements of direct democracy and representative democracy. The civilians had a precise and supreme selection (Montesquieu, p.114) but the management must be undertaken by qualified people. Direct democracy comes from the decision of the entire people, but representative democracy could make things progress properly and in order. That was the rule of law democracy which crystallized all of Montesquieu's thoughts on equality, freedom and democracy.

In short, as the proponent of the ideological liberation movement, Montesquieu accomplished an historical task excellently in the struggle against autocracy, political power abuse and spiritual dictatorship, laid the theoretical foundation for the entire French Enlightenment movement. The French bourgeois revolution of 1789 with the premise of thought and theory of Montesquieu in particular and of the French Enlighteners in general won, overthrew feudal autocracy and brought workers from the position of civilians to the position of citizens. Along with other Enlighteners, Montesquieu's political thought, especially the thought on natural rights, democracy and decentralization, became the foundation of the modern rule-of-law state, the theoretical basis of the two most famous constitutions in human history, namely Constitution 1787 of the United States and Constitution 1791 of France, and was an

important content of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Some Set Issues for the Practice of Building the Rule of Law in Vietnam

The history of the rule-of-law state began after the bourgeois revolutions, initiated by the Enlightenment movement in England and France in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. All Enlighteners including Montesquieu raised the flag of freedom, equality and democracy in their struggles against feudal autocracy, demanded a "rational state" based on the principle of respect of human dignity and natural rights. Building the rule-of-law state was the only option for democracies today.

The term rule-of-law state was first used by the Germans in the mid-nineteenth century, derived from the phrase Rechtsstaat, then continued to be inherited and developed by the British and French, until now this issue has been still controversial. In order to reach a consensus in political understanding and action, the Report of the Secretary-General on the Rule of Law and Transitional Justice in Conflict and Post-Conflict Societies, some norms on the rule-of-law state were proposed [Report of the Secretary-General on the Rule of Law and Transitional Justice in Conflict and Post-Conflict Societies, (S/2004/616), <http://www.un.org>]. Based on that, it could be seen that, although each country had its own political form and different ideologies, a state called the rule-of-law state must meet three basic criteria: firstly, recognize and enforce human rights in practice; secondly, the law must be placed in the supreme position, stand above all other standards and principles of society; thirdly, the relative division of state power among power units to avoid power manipulation.

Building a rule-of-law state in Vietnam towards the objective of prosperous people, strong nation, democracy, justice and civilization is an indispensable and objective demand, meeting the requirements of the era - the era of globalization, integration and development.

The thought on a rule-of-law state in Vietnam was initiated by Ho Chi Minh and expressed in Constitution 1946 [Constitution of the

Democratic Republic of Vietnam 1946, Articles 6, 11, 32, 70] was the application in a certain degree of achievement of the world's ideological civilization and rule of law practice in the specific conditions of the Vietnamese revolution through different historical periods, clearly demonstrating the inevitability of inheritance, and building a rule-of-law state as an irreversible trend. This thought continued to be recognized through the Constitutions and affirmed in the Documents of the Communist Party of Vietnam in the renovation period (see 9).

However, it's a huge gap from idea to reality, and from theory to practice. It does not mean that the existence of the theory of the rule-of-law state would lead to the existence of a rule-of-law state. The fact shows that the construction and reform of the state apparatus, improvement of the legal system, etc. in Vietnam for recent years have gained some remarkable achievements, but in our opinion, it's still an apparatus of bureaucracy with inefficient operation and lack of dynamism. This is reflected in the cumbersome and overlapping state agencies and organizations; the loss of democracy and violation of legitimate rights and interests of people in many places are quite serious at times. The law in social life has not really been highly respected. There are many reasons for those limitations, but first of all, we think that the main reason is in the political system, in the political mechanism. The influences of old ideology, patriarchal and directive management style of wartime are still clearly imprinted in social life, in the way of thinking and doing of a large number of leading officials. Many officials are used to operating by orders and power; little regarding the law. While many people still have the habit of obedience but not ready to accept the responsibility of leading. All of the above manifestations are major obstacles in the current political reform work in Vietnam.

The conception of a rule-of-law state in Vietnam was officially recognized in the Constitution and in the Documents of the general assembly periods of the Communist Party of Vietnam, but since the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, now the the Socialist

Republic of Vietnam was established more than 70 years ago, the rule-of-law state has been still a hot issue. Building a rule-of-law state in Vietnam requires the unremitting efforts of the whole political system, but first of all the determination, courage and political capability of the ruling party. Building the rule-of-law state of Vietnam in accordance with the characteristics of the times in the trend of globalization, international economic integration is an irresistible choice of the Vietnamese revolution.

One of the differences between the rule of law and the totalitarian state was that the rule-of-law state was a state in which the law is at a supreme position. The law in the rule-of-law state is not the subjective will or the arbitrary will of the individual or the ruling party, but the common reason of all citizens is legalized; is a means to ensure human freedom, not a tool to enslave and dominate people.

Demand for freedom, democracy and civil rights in Vietnam has posed a requirement for building a clean, strong government that has a complete legal system in order to harmonize and balance the social relations, settle disagreements between countries and civil society. Therefore, the law must become a tool to restraint state power. The state puts itself under the law not above and beyond the law. In fact, in Vietnam, the awareness and law enforcement have still had many shortcomings, not kept up with the requirements of society, especially the rapid development of the economy and the increasingly strong internationalization process, requiring a corresponding legal institution to promptly resolve social conflicts arising. In law enforcement, there is still contempt for the law, power abuse, which angers in public opinion and threats to the existence of the institution. Montesquieu, nearly 300 years ago, once observed: "In a democracy, when the law is not obeyed, it is when the mechanism of the republic has broken down, the state is no longer a state" (Montesquieu, p.32). Law, therefore, is not only to maintain the existence of society but also to maintain the existence of the state itself; beyond the limits of the law, the state will degenerate and become strange from society.

The rule-of-law state is a state built in the principle of respecting human values, rights and freedom. Human rights, freedom and citizenship are both the objectives, tasks of state activities and a criterion for assessing the nature and extent of the rule of law. The principle of the rule of law is that all powers of the state are aimed at serving the people. The people exercise their power through the Constitution and democratic law. Law is a contract entered into between the state and the people to enforce the people's legitimate rights and interests. The law in the rule-of-law state not only ensures that each citizen is completely free and equal in all opportunities, but also free and equal to the state; The state must not arbitrarily interfere in personal life.

The Constitution of Vietnam stated: "All state power belongs to the people" (Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam 2015, p. 9). However, besides the recorded achievements of the rule of law, the limited manifestations and violations of the people's democratic rights are not particular, even quite serious in some places; The state of "ambiguous" law of many people leads to the fact that they do not know what rights they have, what they can do and what they can't do, and many people in the public power apparatus take advantage of the "ambiguity of the law" of the people as well as loopholes in the law to give themselves the right to harass and act illegally; and the democratic slogan: people know, people discuss, people do and people inspect is legally regulated on the rights and obligations of the people to the state and to the society, so it's just an empty and symbolic slogan. The disregard for the rule of law and power abuse to violate human and civil rights by public authorities is a manifestation of the degeneration of democracy. Of course, it does not mean that the existence of the law and full enforcement of the provisions of the law leads to the existence of a rule-of-law state. Respecting and protecting the law must be synonymous with respecting and protecting rights, legitimate interests and freedom of human.

Finally, an important fundamental principle of the rule of law is the decentralization in the organization of state power. The principle of decentralization requires that the legislative, executive and judicial power branches must be clearly demarcated and

operate relatively independently. Such division of rights is intended to facilitate the rights to control, dominate and coordinate with each other in a harmonious way, avoiding the bureaucracy, authoritarianism and autocracy and arbitrariness of public authorities.

In Vietnam, not only during the long years of the bureaucratic and subsidized centralized mechanism that did not recognize decentralization in the organization and operation of the state apparatus, but also during the period of national renewal and deep integration into international economic life, decentralization was still a new, strange and difficult thing to accept in the country's culture and politics. The Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam defines: state power is unified, with assignment and coordination among state agencies in the exercise of legislative, executive and judicial powers (Clause 3, Article 2 of Constitution 2013) officially recognized the principle of organizing and operating state power in a centralized manner.

Centralization or centralization mechanism - socialist centralism, the foundation for organizing a proletariat government was used in Vietnam during the period of the resistance war and made certain contributions. But now, the country has entered the period of renewal and deep integration into the global economy - politics, the political system is based on the "creeds" and administrative orders of the bureaucratic and subsidy period that were no longer appropriate, hindering the development process... Therefore, from theoretical perspective and practical perspective, "centralization", whether it is "minority centralization" or "majority centralization", the power centralization is always in the potential danger of dictatorship, tyranny, undemocracy and lawlessness, especially the issue of embezzlement, bribery, corruption, insensitivity and moral degradation of a large number of officials in public authorities in Vietnam today are the result of that situation.

The Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam recognizes that state power is unified, in our opinion, this is a principled affirmation of the nature of state power (a matter of all states in history). However, an undeniable fact is being

given to clarify, and the debate about the phrase "unified" with the nature of that state power has always been a hot spot in the debates. The biggest question is: on what principle does the Vietnamese rule of law organize the power system? If it's said that in terms of class nature, state power is always unified in the hands of the ruling class. In Vietnam, state power belongs to the working class and labor population under the leadership of the Communist Party, so state power is unified. Such understanding is not wrong (because in the end, the State is always the product of a certain class, the economically ruling class), but this argument proves to be quite "coercive", subjective and imposed if "referred to" under the modern viewpoint of state power. In fact, the "unification" of power is not a unique feature of the socialist state. Because, right from its inception, state power itself is unified entity consisting of three legislative, executive and judicial branches, regardless of the constitutional type of the states, it still has to perform all functions of a state. As for understanding that the unification of power is as state power belonging to a certain class or party, is it true that state power in a socialist state is exercised under the principle of centralization of power?

The socialist state of Vietnam is a tool for the Vietnamese people that has been constitutionalized and legalized, is the confirmation of the fundamental principles of the rule of law, so state power can't be "unified" in the (centralized) sense but must be decentralized. "Decentralization of power" does not only mean the "assignment" of power in terms of pure functions in a way that an individual or an organization holds all power and assigns a dependent body (agency) to exercise a part of that power. The above "assignment" of power is not, in essence, a characteristic of the rule of law state - decentralization, although decentralization can't be done without assignment (empowerment, coordination between power branches). Decentralization, in the most general sense, is a "technology" of power, is the professionalization and specialization of functions and tasks of branches of state power to control and balance power. It is a mechanism to balance, check and

regulate each other between the legislative, executive and judicial branches, in order to prevent from the abuse of power by public authorities, the cause of the degeneration of state power. Decentralization is the most concentrated expression of a democratic culture. A state without decentralization is not a rule-of-law state.

Conclusion

Building a rule-of-law state in Vietnam is an urgent requirement, derived from the socialist nature (any power in the country belongs to the people), and at the same time is an objective trend of the era. The era of market economy and civil society requires the state to change the way it governs accordingly.

From studying Montesquieu's thought on the rule of law, we have some recommendations that we think are useful in the process of building, reforming, renovating and reorganizing the state power system in Vietnam at the moment as follows:

Firstly, combining decentralization with enhancing the role of "soft power", i.e the critical system of social classes. The social environment is only truly stable once the people's psychology is released, political positivity is raised, and the role of social criticism is respected. Political stability as a condition for development lies not only in the formal consensus among the elements of the system, among classes, between the government and citizens, but also in the sustainable internal structure of the system that is unmoved by external influences. In "About the spirit of the law", Montesquieu once mentioned this kind of soft power, when he declared "The people have the supreme power..." (Montesquieu, p.26), "the people are kings because they can express their will", "having the supreme power must do, on its own, what can be done well" (Montesquieu, p.26). The principle of "people know, people discuss, people do, people inspect and supervise" need to be concretized to prevent from abuse of power and political degeneration.

Secondly, instead of being passionately deep with the chorus of "promoting democracy", it is

necessary to combine the implementation of democracy with the democratization process in fields where democracy is still a formality or has not been applied thoroughly, as pointed out by the 12th Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam (Communist Party of Vietnam 2016, p.168). Once democracy is put in a state of "going nowhere", it is difficult to find comparative indicators in all areas of social life. In our opinion, only when combining these two issues, the driving force of new development is always energised, which means that the issue of democracy is defined in both breadth and depth. Democratization goes hand in hand with democracy promotion - this may sound contradictory at first, but they are actually two sides of unified, interconnected process. On the one hand, the nature of the political regime that Vietnam is building includes the values of democracy, moreover, the democratic values are filtered and evaluated from the history of the struggle for independence and country building. On the other hand, finding a suitable development model requires step-by-step transformation of problems arising in the process of implementing democracy, making democracy more deeply penetrated into social life, which is also the fuel for momentum of development.

Thirdly, continue to innovate the method of controlling power. In order for the rule of law in a democratic state to be constantly improved and enhanced, the issue of power control needs to be renewed. Montesquieu's approach to decentralization in Vietnam is called the *trias politica* principle (separation of powers model) (not suitable for political practice in Vietnam), but it is actually an effective restraint of power, in our understanding, which is the dialectic of power. How is power controlled to demonstrate the power of the rule of law in the principle that "State power is unified with assignment, coordination and control among state agencies" (Constitution of the Republic of Socialist Vietnam (2015), p. 9) so that power is not abused and dominated by group interest? and becomes the driving force of socio-economic development?

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